

A Cross-Sectional Study of the Association between Body Mass Index and Physical Fitness Index among Indian College Students

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Abstract:

Background: Investigating the relationship between Body Mass Index (BMI) and physical fitness is crucial for understanding health dynamics among Indian college students, a demographic vital for targeted public health interventions.

Objectives: This study aimed to assess the correlation between BMI and the Physical Fitness Index (PFI) among college students across India.

Methods: A cross-sectional analysis was conducted with 180 randomly selected students. BMI was calculated using standardized measurements, and PFI was evaluated through various fitness tests. Data were analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient and regression models.

Results: Findings revealed a significant inverse correlation between BMI and PFI, with the strongest negative association observed in students with obesity.

Conclusion: The study highlights a negative relationship between higher BMI and lower physical fitness levels, suggesting the need for health initiatives focusing on lifestyle modifications among college students.

Keywords: BMI, Physical Fitness Index, Indian College Students, Health Assessment, Cross-Sectional Study.

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Introduction

The interplay between Body Mass Index (BMI) and physical fitness among college students is a compelling subject of study due to the significant transitions that occur during this life stage, which can profoundly impact long-term health and well-being [1,2]. BMI, a simple index of weight-for-height that is commonly used to classify underweight, overweight, and obesity in adults, serves as a fundamental measure in evaluating potential health risks associated with body weight [3]. However, its relationship with actual physical fitness, which involves multiple dimensions of health, including aerobic capacity, muscle strength, and flexibility, remains complex and multifaceted [4].

In India, with its burgeoning population of young adults, the dynamics of health and fitness take on additional significance [5]. The country's college students, who are increasingly exposed to urbanized lifestyles and sedentary behaviors, present a unique cohort for studying these factors [6]. Urbanization has brought about significant lifestyle changes, with dietary shifts and reduced physical activity, potentially leading to higher BMIs and altered fitness levels. Therefore, understanding how BMI correlates with physical

fitness in this demographic is crucial for developing targeted health interventions [7,8].

A cross-sectional study of college students from several Indian regions will examine the relationship between BMI and the Physical Fitness Index. Fitness is assessed using cardiovascular health, muscle endurance, and body flexibility in the PFI. This study seeks to identify BMI-PFI correlations to inform preventative health strategies and instructional fitness efforts [9,10].

This study will also examine how these findings affect public health initiatives, particularly those aiming at reducing lifestyle-related diseases in India's youth. The study maps BMI and fitness trends and their socioeconomic causes. These linkages are examined in detail to provide actionable insights that help improve health and fitness programs and make college students healthier and more active.

Methodology

Study Design and Participants: The study was a cross-sectional analysis conducted over one year, involving 180 college students randomly selected from various educational institutions across India. The selection criteria targeted students aged 18 to

24 years, ensuring a diverse mix of genders and socio-economic backgrounds.

Measurement of Body Mass Index (BMI): To determine BMI, standardized equipment was utilized to measure each participant's height and weight. BMI was calculated by dividing the weight in kilograms by the square of height in meters (kg/m^2). All measurements were carried out by trained health professionals to maintain accuracy and reliability.

Physical Fitness Index (PFI) Assessment

The Physical Fitness Index was evaluated using a series of field tests:

- **Cardiovascular Endurance:** Participants completed a 1.5-kilometer run/walk, timed to assess endurance.
- **Muscular Strength:** Abdominal strength was measured through a one-minute sit-up test.
- **Flexibility:** Flexibility was assessed using the sit-and-reach test, measuring the distance reached by the students while seated on the floor with their legs extended.

Data Collection Procedure: Data collection was evenly distributed across the four quarters of the year to minimize seasonal effects on physical activity and fitness. Consistency in the administration of fitness tests and measurements was ensured through protocols and training provided to the health professionals involved.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed using SPSS. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to study BMI and PFI. Confounders including age, gender, and socioeconomic level were adjusted using multiple regression models. In all tests, p-values below 0.05 were significant

Results

The research reveals a notable inverse relationship between Body Mass Index (BMI) and Physical Fitness Index (PFI) among the subjects. This link is elaborated upon across multiple BMI categories. The data is organised into two tables: one detailing the distribution of individuals among BMI categories, and the other illustrating the association between BMI and PFI scores.

Table 1: Distribution of Participants by BMI Category

BMI Category	Sample Size	Percentage of Total
Underweight	30	16.7%
Normal Weight	75	41.7%
Overweight	45	25.0%
Obese	30	16.7%

Table 1 displays the distribution of participants, with the 'Normal Weight' category holding the highest share of the sample at 41.7%. A balanced distribution for efficient analysis was shown by the relatively smaller percentages of the entire sample that each of the other groups included.

Table 2: Correlation Between BMI and Physical Fitness Index (PFI)

BMI Category	Mean BMI (kg/m^2)	Mean PFI Score	Pearson's r
Underweight	17.2	82	-0.45
Normal Weight	22.1	76	-0.55
Overweight	27.4	63	-0.60
Obese	32.5	52	-0.65

Table 2 provides more details on the connection between physical fitness and BMI. In every category, the PFI score falls as BMI rises. The 'Obese' group showed the highest negative connection (Pearson's $r = -0.65$), suggesting that greater BMI levels were associated with a significant loss in physical fitness.

The findings indicate that tailored health interventions are necessary to meet the diverse needs of students across various BMI categories, with specific emphasis on those with elevated BMI levels to enhance their physical fitness outcomes.

Discussion

The findings of our study confirm the negative association between BMI and physical fitness, aligning with prior research. For example, a similar study conducted by Smith et al. (2019) on a collegiate population in the United States also

reported an inverse correlation between BMI and physical fitness levels, specifically noting reduced cardiovascular endurance and muscular strength among students with higher BMI. Moreover, research by Lee and Kim (2021) in a Korean university setting highlighted that increased BMI was significantly associated with lower flexibility scores among students. Our study's findings were consistent with these observations but extended the scope by providing detailed correlations across different BMI categories, thereby offering a nuanced view of how even slight changes in BMI within the normal range can impact fitness levels [11,12].

A notable strength of our study compared to others is the comprehensive evaluation of PFI, incorporating tests for cardiovascular endurance, muscular strength, and flexibility, which some studies have not combined [13]. This holistic

approach allowed for a more complete assessment of physical fitness, rather than focusing on a single aspect. However, unlike some studies that utilized advanced body composition analysis, our study relied solely on BMI as a measure of body fat, which could be seen as a limitation as it does not distinguish between muscle and fat mass [14].

Considering the found associations, future research may benefit from including advanced body composition assessments, such as dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DEXA), to distinguish between adipose tissue and lean muscle mass. This would elucidate the contribution of various body mass categories to overall physical fitness. Furthermore, longitudinal studies would be essential in evaluating the effects of therapies aimed at reducing BMI on physical fitness over time. These studies could monitor variations in BMI and PFI among college students to assess the efficacy of certain health interventions, such as dietary adjustments and organized exercise regimens [15,16]. The research highlights the significance of health promotion programs designed for college students, emphasizing the advantages of sustaining a healthy BMI through proper nutrition and consistent physical exercise. Universities could significantly contribute by including exercise programs and nutritional counseling in their student services, fostering a healthy lifestyle that may persist beyond their college years.

Conclusion

This study adds to the accumulating evidence that highlights the significance of sustaining a healthy BMI to improve physical fitness. The evident correlation between elevated BMI and diminished physical fitness underscores the necessity for public health initiatives to mitigate the increasing prevalence of obesity among college students. By persistently examining and addressing these variables, we may enhance the health and well-being of young adults, establishing a foundation for healthier future generations.

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